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Aging in Place: Issues and Challenges

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[Places have enormous to offer during childhood, youth and old age. Childhood is nourished as potential, youth used as resource but elderly is being assumed or in reality as burden in later life raises the question of issues and challenges encompassing aging in place [AIP]. Options willingly or unwillingly which constraints and provide opportunity in later life is AIP or moving out of place which are distinctly different from the experiences of elderly aging at home with 'place' having its own dynamics. AIP is defined as the ability to live in one's own home and community safely, independently and comfortably regardless of age, income or ability level [Centre of Disease Control and prevention 2013] while moving out of place is the need of assisted living with declining control over space. It offers continuity with bonds of family and friends ever evaluating age friendliness of place without overlooking the unique cultural context. The decision to move out of place is collectivistic or the individual vis-à-vis role of asset continues to play vital role. However, great adjustment is shown by elderly females to adapt to barriers. The adjustment also redefines meaning of ageing in place as ageing in right place AIRP with emphasis on unique tailor friendly environment that engages in programme to view place as dynamic and active agent. So, interaction is neither biologically determined nor discursive but co formation.]

Researches have reported that majority of elderlies wish to age in place so that they can explore their life in their own ways where family and friends also matter for them [AARP 2011]. John Costa- Font's [2009] observation of aging in place shows how a representative Spanish population prefer AIP. This study portrays the preference for AIP when they grew older their attachment also becomes stronger to their place of aging. The studies throw light on lesser attachments to AIP for those who are affluent. Similar is the case with highly educated elderlies, they prefer not to accompany relatives but move out of place. Hence, it is seen that being affluent and highly educated promotes to move out of place in spite of having rich resources to remain in-situ and cherish their lives.

Underlying elderlies' desire to aging in place or moving out of place may be due to age friendliness of the place

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of choice, in most cases it is the place where they have spent few years of their life before superannuation. They tend to draw themselves nearer to the AIP, if it is safer and accessible. For instance, WHO'S [1997] age - friendly communities guidelines identify eight domains of friendliness which are to be considered for planning for all age- groups; outdoor spaces, transportation, housing, social participation, respect and social inclusion, civic participation, communication and health services [AARP,2017].

Literature also suggests to encourage better ageing in place, it lays emphasis on engagement in various activities spread across multiple generation [Quinn and Judd]. This helps in reduction in social isolation and enhancement of healthy well-being [Productivity Commission, 2011]. Consequently, Claudia Baldwin of University of Sunshine Coast observed South East Queensland, Australia came out with a significant result of aging in neighbourhood concept with a participatory

approach culminating in a better planning for communities [Baldwin et.al. 2012].

Further, AIP contributes to the wellbeing and promote it as a policy for both developed and developing countries [WHO, 2007]. It gives a sense of attachment, connectedness, identity, independence and autonomy. According to Terry Lum [2016] explores the Chinese society in terms of unique culture and social background and tries to correlate to their preference for AIP. There is strong inclination to AIP due to filial piety and sense of multi-generation under one roof creating cohesiveness. In this way, Indian society as joint family could also be explored as the root of Indian families is joint has changed over a period of time to become nuclear family but in reality, it deceives to some extent so that characteristic of joint family is practiced.

In Lum's [2016] study of Special Administrative Region of Hong Kong experiences declining family size and cohesiveness too implying lack of aging in place. Hence, looking into elderlies throughout the world as a single homogenous group could be misleading and the policies should be tailor made in local in-situ program for better experiences.

So far then, research evidence explored age friendliness and socio demographic profile in traditional and developed world showing varied experiences. Our search for all encompassing on varied population from above finds barriers in form of values and socio demographic characteristics. Further, for different challenges faced by differently abled elderlies could be found in tailor made solutions.

Nevertheless, as all societies are on a different level of evolution with unique cultural and societal background reflecting differently empowered elderlies. Takeshi Nakagawa [2022] argues that in Asia autonomous decision making is not acceptable whether the ageing in place have all the attributes of age- friendliness or not. It is not decided by the elderly in question but it is a collectivistic culture to decide AIP or moving out of place. Elderlies' decision matters less than family and clinicians, especially when one is bedridden it becomes more vulnerable to face the outcome not under one's control. The case in the traditional society is still not homogenous.

Assets compiled throughout life by Japanese could be more than assets of an Indian elderly, still the collective decision seems option in both cases. For instance, majority of elderly Australians owners of their own houses intended to age in place [Australian government, bulletin 114, 2013]. But in future proportions of aged with own asset is expected to decline. Still, location have sense of attachment for older people to decide whether to live in AIP or to move beyond. Further, it becomes

clearer when it is seen that private renters have tendency to move out of place.

Other research re-emphasizes those financial considerations are important too in making decision [Louis Batera, 2019]. For instance, some elderly wish to move to a retirement community to participate in social activities while number of elderlies are opting to stay where they were. This is decided on the basis of their financial preparation they have done during their lives transition. Some assume assisted community living could be costlier than AIP. Butera wealth management professionals study the case-to-case basis to help in decision making for unique situation.

Similarly, Aging in Place Challenge Program [2021] is a Canadian government program on improving the wellbeing of elderly and personal caregiver through a sustainable model for preventing Home and Community Health Care. The crux of the program is to enable nursing homes for elderly with highest needs. This helps in reducing cost to the Canadian Healthcare system. This suggests through recent researches in Canada if given the choice 85% preferred AIP and this program assists in doing so through technology and innovation. Here, assets of individuals are neutralized through provisions of AIP Challenge Program.

Another study conducted by Johnson [2017] also offers further evidence in favour of AIP in USA. Johnson's analysis clearly states elderlies' obsession to AIP regarding their wishes, implying promotion of places of dwelling to be made as friendly as possible. It gives thrust on modification of housing units at individual level and walkways, crossing, signals, parks at community level.

Dwelling units suitable for aged American population should be build which has now five generations -Pre boomers, boomers, generation x, generation y and generation z. Building dwelling units which enable to create compatible place as per the needs of living together which generates and nourishes interaction in golden years. Place as sense of attachment is seen as group attribute featuring collective actions.

Researchers have proposed several ways to explore AIP .For instance, if AIP is comfortably living in one's own home as opposed to nursing home or residential care - facilities then ageing in the right place[AIRP] is extending the horizon of definition of AIP in response to providing solution to low income and weak health conditions of elderly .AIRP includes elderly with variety of needs to sustain their independence , autonomy, social connectedness, competency and control over space [Humanities and Social Sciences 2021 ,e-book]

However, increasing the horizon of definition of AIP could be a theoretical solution at first instance but in

practice it comes closer to preparation for an elderly population facilitating active aging as proposed by WHO culminating in to global age friendly cities guide requirement. It captures a framework for cities and communities to develop and adapt to the needs of elderly.

The city of Calgary followed a senior age-friendly strategy as per the global age-friendly cities guide but also tailor made through a community engagement process [Adibba Adal, 2021]. It has well -informed municipal policy on aging in place. It includes areas for social interaction, a meaningful symbolic environment, and web-based housing interventions. It also offers senior services home maintenance program through special needs assistance.

Indeed, AIP is the guiding spirit addressing the needs of the elderly. It is an approach to peep into the interaction of the individual and the environment and how both mutually coexist to shape AIP. The term 'Place' is multifaceted as physical it can be seen, as social - individuals are connected, as psychological - has sense of belonging and attachment and as cultural has values, beliefs and meanings. Places hold history, bring precise life history of individuals and their identities together. When house is converted into home; the time taken to do so creates a lively interaction with place and inmate forming desire for AIP. The policies could be seen as intrusion in private life of individual and the war to create Utopia for aged is to stop or minimise this intrusion as long as possible.

The revision and redefinition of AIP is about optimising charms of AIP with least input from outside. Gillard et al. [2007] found as mobility decreased, attachments increased while Wiles et al. [2011] examined as number of choices the age increased attachment to place also increased. In crux, ultimate goal is to control their lives. In contrast, moving to nursing homes is seen as a loss of control and independence [Clarity, 2007]. It seems the government and policy-makers' belief in AIP is to reduce the expenses of institutional care and the elderly also seems to converge to AIP for their control over lives [Chappel et. al., 2004]. This creates an integrated momentum towards AIP. Not surprisingly, policies have reflected this desire, may be in different words.

If Rowles propounded a theory of insideness to show the attachment to place bearing a sense of control, social relationships and memories of identities, then Lawton shows the increase in environmental influence forces the functional ability to decrease. It requires a match between personal competency and environmental press. Our thinking spirals, sprawls and sprung to evolve the aged bearing sublime mind, healthy body and fruitful output.

In conclusion, the issues and challenges of AIP is a complex phenomenon. On the one hand, evidence demonstrate that the place has immense to offer to elderly. The bonds of family and friends juxtaposed with physical domain of a 'place' creates balance as per the needs of the aged. Secondly, the decision is not objective on the basis of accessibility and availability of favourable factors, but cultural background of the place play a major role. The domains of friendliness of a place have favourable and unfavourable factors. In turn, it also gets shaped by the adaptation to the need of elderly and meaning assigned to the social environment of aged.

Place is multi- dimensional connotation, it is physical, psychological and cultural - all in one. Policies are imposed and at the same time ideally gets shaped by the engagement of protagonists. Challenges are many but programs are varied as per need of people of that place

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